

Participatory Evaluation of Sesame (*Sesamum indicum* L.) Varieties in the Gamo and Gofa Zones of Southern Region Parts of Ethiopia

Demelash Bassa Belayneh ✉

Areka Agricultural Research Center, P.O.BOX. 79, Areka, Ethiopia

Yasin Goa Chondie

Southern Agricultural Research Institute, P.O.BOX. 6, Hawassa, Ethiopia

Dembele Ersulo Aloto

Arbaminich Agricultural Research Center, P.O.BOX. 21, Arbaminich, Ethiopia

Abstract

Sesame, an important oil crop in Ethiopia, is a warm-season, annual short-day plant. However, its productivity and production are hindered by the absence of recommended improved varieties in the study areas. Consequently, a trial was conducted from 2019 to 2020 to evaluate ten improved sesame varieties using Randomized Complete Block Design, with farmers as replications, aiming to identify those with higher yields. The plots were 4 meters long, containing 6 rows spaced 0.4m apart, and plants spaced 0.1m apart, with a seed rate of 5kg/ha. Plot sizes were 9.6m² (2.4m by 4m). ANOVA results for sesame varieties grown in single or combined environments revealed a significant difference ($P < 0.05$) in grain yield, days to 50% flowering, days to 50% maturity, capsule per plant, thousand seed weight, and plant height. Sesame varieties like Setit-1, Setit-2, and Setit-3, characterized by early flowering, showed mean yields ranging from 424 to 555kg/ha, recommended for drought-prone areas. Conversely, late-flowering varieties like Dangur, Obsa, Gondar, and respective local checks yielded from 602.06 to 639.06kg/ha in the tested environments. Consequently, based on the results, early and late-flowering sesame varieties were recommended for drought-prone and potential areas of the Gamo and Gofa zones, respectively, and similar agro-ecological zones in the country, provided other weather and related factors remain constant.

Keywords: *oil crops, sesame, cultivation potential areas, agro-ecological zones, varieties, yield.*

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Introduction

Sesame (*Sesamum indicum* L. $2n=26$) is an annual oil crop characterized by a short growing season. It is known as “queen of oil seeds”; it is esteemed for its high-quality, unsaturated, and stable oil content (Terefe et al., 2012; Monitor, 2012). Ethiopia produces sesame of exceptionally high quality globally (Fiseha and Muez, 2019). In production, China, India, Myanmar, and Ethiopia ranked 1st, 2nd, 3rd, and 4th respectively in the world (MOA, 2019). The primary cultivation regions for sesame seeds are in the northern and northwest areas of Ethiopia, with respective production areas in Tigray, Amhara, Oromia, Benishangul Gumuz, and SNNPR documented as 120,855.45 ha, 169,988.58 ha, 82,018.04 ha, 40,722.60 ha, and 6,365.70 ha. The corresponding productivities are 0.704, 0.66, 0.735, 0.68, and 0.497 tons per

hectare (CSA, 2020). In the 2020/21 season, sesame was cultivated on 369,897.32 hectares, yielding an estimated production of 260,257.633 tons (EAA, 2020).

Ethiopia, currently ranked fourth in global markets, stands as one of the leading sesame exporters. Between 2000 and 2013, the country exported 2,159.734 tons of sesame, generating earnings of 2,621,042 USD, making it a significant export oil crop (Abdi Berhaneh, 2018; Tewdros et al., 2021). The trading platform facilitates the exchange of grade 1, 2, and 3 for Wollega sesame, along with grades 1 and 2 for Humera sesame (MOA, 2019). Ethiopia's sesame production encompasses three distinct varieties: Humera, Gondar, and Wollega, with Humera Sesame seed constituting the majority of the countries' export (CSA, 2020).

From a nutrition perspective, sesame serves as a food ingredient, with its dried seeds commonly consumed in soups and regarded as a favored dessert in Africa and Asia, especially when paired with sugar. Additionally, sesame is utilized as both a cooking and salad oil and plays a role in the production of cooking fats and margarine. Despite the economic and nutritional significance of sesame in the producing areas, such as the Gamo and Gofa zones in the southern region of Ethiopia, improved varieties of sesame have not been introduced into these study areas (Abdi Berhane, 2018). Despite the Ethiopia national agricultural research system releasing more than twenty sesame varieties for nationwide production (Tewdros et al., 2021), these released varieties have not yet been integrated into the production systems of the study areas. Consequently, this trial was conducted to identify superior-performing varieties in terms of yield and other traits preferred by farmers, aiming to recommend them for production.

Materials and Method

Description of the Study Area

The experiment took place in southern Ethiopia, specifically at the Borda research station in Gofa and the Arbaminich research station in Gamo, as well as in corresponding farmer fields, across two growing seasons from 2019 to 2020. The Gofa zone's Borda site is situated at an elevation of 1349 meters above sea level, with coordinates at longitude 36°89'17"E and latitude 6°03'60"N. Meanwhile, the Arbaminich site is positioned at an altitude of 1229 meters above sea level, with coordinates at longitude 37°59'17"E and latitude 6°01'56"N. Annual rainfall in Gofa and Gamo zones amounted to 669mm and 544mm, respectively. Figures 1 and 2 below illustrate the temperature and Potential Evapotranspiration (PET) at the Gofa and Gamo zone trial stations, respectively.

Figure 1. Temperature (°C) and PET (mm) of Gofa Zone, Borda Trial Station
Source: FAO, 2005.

Figure 2: Temperature (°C) and PET (Potential Evapotranspiration) of Gamo Zone Trial
 Source: FAO, 2005.

Experimental Design and Cultural Practices

During the 2019-2020 growing seasons, the experiment took place in both environments, specifically under rain-fed conditions. Using four farmers as replications, a Randomized Complete Block Design (Table 1) was employed to lay out ten sesame varieties-nine released and one local check. Measurements were taken for the seed yields and other yield-related traits of these varieties. Each treatment was randomly assigned and sown in six rows, each measuring 4 meters long, with a spacing of 0.4 meters between rows and 0.1 meters between plants. Consequently, the dimensions were 2.4 meters by 4 meters in width and length, respectively. Blocks and plots were separated by 1.5 and 0.4 meters, respectively. The seed rate maintained was 5 kg ha⁻¹ in both Gofa and Arbaminich research stations, as well as on the lands of the four farmers.

Table 1. Description of Sesame Varieties Used for the Experiment, 2019-2020

S.N.	Variety name	Released year	Seed Color	Oil content %	Special Trait
1.	Setit-2	2016	White	53.77	Early maturing
2.	Benishangul-1	2016	White	54.10	For drought prone area
3.	Obsa	2010	White	51.10	High yielder
4.	Mechal	-	Pale white		
5.	Dangur	2015	Gray	56.96	High yielder
6.	Acc-051-02-sel-1- (2))	2016	White	50.4	For drought prone area
7.	HuARC-4(Setit-3)	2017	White	54.42	Early maturing
8.	Gondar -1	2016	Pale white	50.00	High yielder
9.	Setit -1 (SC)	2011	White	54.00	Early maturing
10.	Local check	-			

Source: MOA, 2019.

Note: SC= Standard check

Data Collection

In the data collection process, essential traits such as days to 50% emergence, stand count at emergence and harvest, plant height, number of branches per plant, number of pods/capsules per plant, number of

seeds per capsules, days to 50% flowering, days to 50% maturity, 1000 seed weight, and seed yield per plot in kilograms were considered (IPGRI and NBPGR, 2004).

The trial, planted at each station, functioned as a mother trial from which the researchers obtained their data. Subsequently, baby trials were planted in appropriate areas of the four farmers' land to gather information on their preferences. However, it's important to note that data on the preferences of farmers were not collected from the research stations in Gamo and Gofa.

Days to 50% Flowering (DTF): the number of days starting from planting (from the first day of soil wetting in the case of dry planting) up to 50% of the plants in each plot becomes flowered.

Days to 50% maturity (DTM): the number of days starting from planting up to 50% of the plants in each plot becomes matured.

Plant height at maturity (PH) (cm): this growth parameter is the height of the plants in centimeters (cm) from the ground up to the top of the main stem of the plants.

Number of branches per plant (BPP): number of productive branches with one or more pods

Number of pods/capsules per plant (PPP): refers to the total number of pods in a given plant counted at the time of maturity

Seeds per pod/capsules (SPP): the average number of sesame seeds counted per pod and the average number of seeds collected from five plants and one pod from each plant

Thousand seed weight (gram) (TSW): the average weight of 1000 seeds randomly collected from the harvested grain yield in grams

Grain yield (kg/ha): the total grain yield (kg/ha) harvested from the net plot area

Data Analysis

The SAS version 9.2 software's GLM algorithm (SAS, 2009) was utilized for the statistical analysis of crop seed yield and associated trait data obtained from both locations and corresponding farmers' fields. Mean separation was determined using Fisher's LSD (Least Significant Difference) at a 0.05 probability level (Gomez and Gomez, 1984). Homogeneity of error variance was assessed before combining the Gamo and Gofa zone location data. Using Gen Stat 17th edition (Payne et al., 2012). Subsequently, ANOVA for each location and combined analysis was scrutinized using proc GLM in SAS (SAS, 2009). Additionally, the authors generated Temperature (°C) and PET (mm) figures for Gofa zone and Gamo zone trial stations, utilizing 10 years of raw data from the local climate estimator produced by FAO (2005).

Results and Discussion

The Performance Evaluation of Sesame Varieties

The scrutiny of homogeneity of variance before integrating data from different contexts and years was carried out using Gen Stat 17th Edition (Payne et al., 2012). Additionally, SAS version 9.2's GLM (General Linear Model) procedure was employed to assess normality (SAS, 2009). Based on the analysis of variance, all location analyses, except for seed per plant, indicated a significant difference ($P < 0.05$) for seed yield, days to 50% flowering, days to 50% maturity, number of capsule per plant, thousand seed weight, and plant height of sesame varieties tested in the Gofa zone from 2019 to 2020 (Table 2). In relation to the mentioned traits of sesame varieties, performance evaluation studies conducted in the Northern areas of Ethiopia, such as those by Fiseha and Muez (2019), revealed similar findings.

Table 2. Mean Square of Yield and Related Traits of Sesame Varieties in Gofa Zone of Southern Ethiopia from 2019 to 2020

SV	DF	Mean square values						
		YLD	DTF	PH	DTM	CPPT	SDPPT	TSW
Error	67	56067.023	6.65	148.45	24.19	116.6	1.29	0.17
Trt	9	181986.77*	64.23*	631.67*	24.19*	433.21*	0.75 ^{ns}	0.67*
Rep	3	2482.82	0.75	37.54	4.18	53	2.84	2.05
Mean		617.52	51.07	128.81	129.16	35.47	4.53	2.42
LSD		265.1	133.16	12.16	6.39	9.55	0.78	0.133
CV		38.34	5.04	9.45	4.083	30.47	25.05	16.97

Note: CV= coefficient of variation, LSD=Least Significant Difference, Rep= replication, Trt= Treatment, DF=Degree of freedom, YLD= Yield, DTF= Days to 50% flowering, PH=Plant height, DTM= Days to 50% maturity. CPPT=Capsule per plant, SDPPT=Seed per plant, TSW=Thousand Seed Weight

There was a significant difference ($P < 0.05$) in all parameters, excluding seed per pod/capsule, which encompassed days to 50% maturity, seed yield (kg ha^{-1}), plant height (cm), number of capsules per plant, thousand seed weight, and days to 50% flowering (Table 3), based on the sesame research conducted in the Gamo zone from 2019 to 2020. Highlighting the performance variations of sesame varieties across diverse regions of Ethiopia, studies by Fiseha and Muez (2019), Tewdros et al. (2019), and Chemedda et al. (2014), focusing on the performance and stability of legume crop varieties, reported similar results. In their genetic progress studies on common bean anthracnose disease, Solomon et al. (2019) reported the significance of yield and yield associated traits.

Table 3. Mean Square of Yield and Related Traits of Sesame Varieties in Gamo Zone of Southern Ethiopia from 2019 to 2020

SV	DF	Mean square values						
		YLD	DTF	PH	DTM	CPPT	SDPPT	TSW
Error	67	18868.076	11.48	572.85	165.04	875	1.29	0.19
Trt	9	42536.21*	27.53*	157.35*	198.55*	903*	0.75 ^{ns}	0.69
Rep	3	17543.67	0.083	163.73	97.65	72	2.85	1.56
Mean		471.51	51.07	151.85	128.23	47.2	4.5	2.5
LSD		137.09	3.38	23.88	12.82	9.5	0.78	0.13
CV		29.13	6.64	15.76	10.01	28.9	24.7	17.67

Note: CV= coefficient of variation, LSD=Least Significant Difference, Rep= replication, Trt= Treatment, DF=Degree of freedom, YLD= Yield, DTF= Days to 50% flowering, PH=Plant height, DTM= Days to 50% maturity, CPPT=Capsule per plant, SDPPT=Seed per plant, TSW=Thousand Seed Weight

The analyses of all ten sesame varieties tested in the Gamo and Gofa zones throughout 2019 and 2020 demonstrated a significant difference between the varieties concerning seed yield (kg), plant height (cm), days to 50% maturity, number of capsules per plant, thousand seed weight, and days to 50% flowering (Table 4). The results indicated significant differences among the tested crop varieties under diverse conditions (Table 4). This finding contrasts with that of Tadesse and Misgana (2017), who observed a non-significant difference among sesame varieties in Southern Ethiopia. Possible reasons for this disparity include variations in the experimental environment or the use of different sesame varieties.

Table 4. Mean Square of Yield and Related Traits of Sesame Varieties in Gamo and Gofa Zones of Southern Ethiopia from 2019 to 2020

SV	DF	Mean square values					
		YLD	DTF	PH	DTM	CPPT	TSW
loc	1	687226	0.001	22896.22	0.001	22231.22	0.225
Rep (loc)	6	13706	0.816	150.74	10.51	62.79	1.80
Yr (loc)	2	1457349	128.455	413.25	48.94	20905.92	0.225
Trt	9	99284*	64.800*	17203.56*	1419.61*	1158.06*	1.35 *
loc*Trt	9	128303*	0.001*	475.57*	0.001*	178.15*	0.02*
Yr*Trt (loc)	18	96293					
CV (%)		23.7	5.20	8.28	3.47	28.90	17.29
Mean		552.96	51.07	140.77	129.16	47.26	2.46
LSD		0.79	1.82	8.15	3.14	9.55	0.133

Note: SV= Source of variation, loc=environment, rep= replication, Yr= year, Trt= treatment, CV= Coefficient of variation, LSD=Least Significant Difference, YLD = Yield, DTF= Days to 50% flowering, DTM= Days to 90% maturity, PH= Plant height, CPPT= Capsule per plant, TSW= Thousand Seed Weight

Table 5 illustrates that there were significant differences among treatments based on the comparison of error means squares, as evident in the yield in kg per hectare, days to 50% flowering, plant height (cm), capsules per plant, thousand seed weight, and days to 50% maturity. The sesame varieties Dangur, Obsa, Gondar-1, and the local check exhibited relatively higher yields (602.06-639.06kg ha⁻¹), equivalent to the national average yield of 600-800kg ha⁻¹, according to the ANOVA, indicating to significant difference in yield performance among sesame varieties (Table 5). Setit-2, Setit-1, and Setit-3 were identified as early-flowering varieties, whereas Dangur, Obsa, and the local check were categorized as late-flowering varieties. Following flowering, certain sesame varieties, such as Obsa, Acc-051-02-sel-1-(2), and the local check, took a relatively longer time to mature (Table 5). Similar results were reported by Fiseha and Muez (2019) in the evaluation of sesame varieties.

Table 5. Mean Separation of Yield and Related Traits of Sesame Varieties in Gamo and Gofa Zones of Southern Ethiopia from 2019 to 2020

Trts.	variety	Mean					
		YLD	DTF	PH	DTM	CPPT	TSW
1.	Setit-2	554.13ab	47.25e	143.37ab	129.75abc	58.8a	2.75a
2.	Benishangul-1	596.19a	55.12a	146.93a	129.87abc	56.7a	2.3bc
3.	Obsa	629.56a	53.62ab	144.31ab	131.00a	40b	2.75a
4.	Mechal	450.75c	50.37cd	142.37ab	126.75c	50.3ab	2.56ab
5.	Dangur	639.06a	54.37a	145.56a	127.25bc	56a	2.56ab
6.	Acc-051-02-sel-1- (2))	464.69bc	51.13c	138.93ab	130.87a	37.6c	2.8a
7.	HuARC -4(Setit-3)	424.63c	48.62de	136.43bc	127.87abc	37.5c	2d
8.	Gondar -1	612.69a	51.87bc	137.06bc	127.00abc	44.2bc	2.25cd
9.	Setit -1 (SC)	555.88ab	47.00e	130.25c	130.25ab	39c	2.56ab
10.	Local	602.06a	51.37c	142.50ab	131.00a	51.8ab	2.06cd

Note: * Means with the same letter are not significantly different, YLD= Yield in kg per hectare, DTF= days to 50% flowering, PH= Plant height, DTM=days to 50% maturity, CPPT=Capsule per plant, TSW=Thousand Seed Weight

Correlation of Seed Yield and Related Traits

There was a weak positive correlation between the number of capsules per plant and days to 50% flowering ($r=0.142$), days to 50% maturity ($r=0.244$), and seed yield ($r=0.017$), but a strong positive correlation with plant height ($r=0.549$). However, the number of capsules per plant exhibited a weak negative correlation with seed per plant ($r=-0.021$) and thousand seed weight ($r= -0.051$). Moreover, days to 50% flowering showed a weak positive correlation with days to maturity ($r=0.211$), seed yield ($r=0.022$), and plant height ($r= 0.273$), but a weak negative correlation with seeds per plant ($r= -0.054$) and thousand seed weight ($r= -0.001$). Days to 50% maturity had a strong positive correlation with plant height ($r= 0.45$) and seed yield ($r=0.404$), but a weak negative and positive correlation with seed per plant ($r= -0.014$) and thousand seed weight ($r = 0.08$), respectively. Plant height exhibited a weak positive correlation with seed yield ($r = 0.236$), but a weak negative correlation with seeds per plant ($r= - 0.177$) and thousand seed weight ($r= - 0.068$). Thus, traits such as capsule per plant, days to 50% flowering, days to 50% maturity, and plant height showed a positive correlation with yield, whereas seeds per capsule and thousand seed weight exhibited a negative correlation with yield. Several authors have shown the correlation between yield and yield-related traits in legumes. Examples include common bean studies by Alemayehu (2010), Ashango et al. (2016), field pea research conducted by Yasin (2007), and investigation on soybean by Fekadu (2008).

Table 6. Spearman's Correlation of Sesame Varieties Seed Yield and Yield Related Traits at Gofa and Gamo Zones, 2020-2021.

	CPPT	DTF	DTM	PH	SDPPT	TSW	Yield
CPPT	1.000						
DTF	0.142	1.000					
DTM	0.244	0.211	1.000				
PH	0.549	0.273	0.45	1.000			
SDPPT	-0.021	-0.054	-0.014	-0.177	1.000		
TSW	-0.051	-0.001	0.080	-0.068	0.174	1.000	
Yield	0.017	0.022	0.404	0.236	-0.103	-0.99	1.000

Conclusion

The analysis of variance for seed yield, days to 50% flowering, days to 50% maturity, number of capsules per plant, thousand seed weight, and plant height confirmed a significant difference among sesame varieties. Among the tested sesame varieties, Dangur exhibited a higher yield. Furthermore, Obsa, Gondar-1, and the local check matured later, suggesting that some sesame varieties had a delayed maturation due to the time taken to fill their seeds, resulting in a higher grain yield. In contrast, the sesame variety Acc-051-02-sel-1-(2) matured later but yielded less. Additionally, Setit-1, Setit-2, and Setit-3 are early-maturing sesame varieties suitable for the same agro-ecological zones as the study and /or regions in the country prone to drought. Similarly, Dangur, Obsa, Gondar-1, and the local checks were recommended for potential areas with expensive sesame production.

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